

STUDY ON MARKETING OF GROUNDNUT IN MANCHERIAL DISTRICT OF TELANGANA

Chintala Manoj Kumar and Mr. Pritesh Dwivedi

Student and Assistant Professor

Department of Agricultural Economics

Sam Higginbottom University of Agriculture, Technology and Sciences

Prayagraj-211007, India

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Abstract

The study was conducted to investigate the marketing channels, marketing costs, margins, price spreads, and challenges involved in the marketing of Groundnut in Mancherial district, Telangana. The sample for the study consisted of 100 farmers and 20 Market Functionaries (10 wholesalers, 5 retailers, and 5 commission agents). Mancherial district was purposely selected as it is a leading district in Telangana for groundnut cultivation. Out of the 16 blocks, Mancherial block was chosen for the study. A list of 20 villages with a significant area under groundnut cultivation was prepared, and 5 villages (Hajipur, Mulkalla, Rapalle, Vempalle, and Gudipet) were purposely selected. All the farmers in the selected villages were listed, and information related to the study was collected using a well-defined and pre-tested schedule through personal interviews or surveys. The data collected pertained to the agricultural year 2021-2022. Tabular analysis, Garrett's ranking technique, marketing cost, margin, and efficiency were employed to analyze the objectives of the study. The findings revealed that Groundnut output is sold through market yards and traders, although some farmers sell directly to traders at the farm gate or village markets, while others use specified marketing channels. Among the problems faced by the farmers, lack of timely market information was ranked first, followed by fluctuations in market prices, involvement of middlemen in marketing, improper weighment, high commission charges, scarcity of labor for transportation and marketing, long distance to markets, absence/insufficient storage facilities, and high cost of transportation. Lack of timely market information was the top-ranked problem identified by the respondents. Farmers expressed concerns about not receiving timely information about market prices from extension personnel and government agencies. Fluctuation in prices was ranked second, as commission agents and traders formed groups and lowered prices whenever there was a surplus quantity in the market, leading to higher profits for commission agents and lower prices for farmers.

Key Words: Groundnut, Constraints, Mancherial district, Mancherial Block, Marketing channels.

Introduction

Agriculture continues to be a crucial sector in the Indian economy, supporting the livelihoods of nearly 70% of the rural population. Well-functioning markets are essential for driving growth, development, and economic prosperity in rural areas of India. To enhance dynamism and efficiency in the marketing system, substantial investments are needed for the development of post-harvest and cold chain infrastructure closer to farmers' fields. The majority of the rural poor are engaged in agriculture-based households, with small and marginal farmers comprising the largest group of cultivators in Indian agriculture. About 85% of operated holdings are smaller than two hectares, and among these holdings, 66% are less than one hectare. However, farmers often face challenges in marketing their produce at fair prices due to the presence of numerous intermediaries in the marketing channels. Consequently, state governments need to amend their respective APMC laws to deregulate the marketing system in India, promote investment in marketing infrastructure, encourage corporate sector participation in direct marketing, and facilitate a national integrated market. The Department of Agriculture and Cooperation has also formulated a model law on agricultural marketing for guidance and adoption by state governments, which includes provisions for the establishment of private markets/yards, direct purchase centers, consumer/farmer's markets for direct sale, and promotion of Public Private Partnership in the management and development of agricultural markets in India.

Groundnut, also known as earthnut, peanut, monkey nut, and manilla nut, is a versatile legume. It ranks as the 13th most important food crop and the 4th most important oilseed crop worldwide. The botanical name for groundnut is *Arachis hypogaea* L., which comes from the Greek words "Arachis" meaning a legume and "hypogaea" meaning below ground, referring to its geocarpic nature of pod formation.

Groundnut kernels are rich in protein, containing about 25% protein, which is 1.3 times higher than meat, 2.5 times higher than eggs, and 8 times higher than fruit. The oil content in groundnut kernels ranges from 40-50%, and it is extensively used for culinary purposes such as cooking oil and vegetable oil (vanaspati). Additionally, groundnut oil

is used in the production of soaps, cosmetics, cold cream, and various industrial applications. The multiple uses of groundnut plants make it an excellent cash crop for both domestic markets and foreign trade in many developing and developed countries. Globally, 50% of groundnuts produced are used for oil extraction, 37% for confectionery use, and 12% for seed purposes.

Research Methodology**Stages**

1. First stage - Selection of district
2. Second stage - Selection of block
3. Third stage - Selection of villages
4. Fourth stage - Selection of respondents
5. Fifth stage - Selection of market
6. Sixth stage - Selection of market functionaries

Selection of the District:

Mancherial is a Mandal located in the state of Telangana. As of 2023, the estimated population of Mancherial Mandal is 257,701. According to the 2011 census of India, the total population of Mancherial Mandal was 195,228, with 99,597 males and 95,631 females. The population of Mancherial was estimated to be 249,892 in 2022. Out of the total population, there are 128,049 literate individuals, with 72,031 males and 56,018 females. The Mandal has a total of 67,919 workers with multiple skills, including 50,881 males and 17,038 females. Among them, there are 2,835 cultivators engaged in agriculture, with 2,094 males and 741 females. Additionally, there are 9,400 people working as agricultural laborers in Mancherial, with 5,039 males and 4,361 females.

Selection of the Block:

Selection of the block is the second stage of sampling, where a complete list of blocks is obtained from the District Headquarters. From this list, Mancherial block will be randomly selected for further sampling.

Selection of the Villages:

Selection of the village is the third stage of sampling. A complete list of villages in the selected block was obtained from the Block Development Office of the concerned block. From this list, 5% of villages were randomly selected for the present study.

S.No	Villages	No. of Farmers
1	Hajipur	28

2	Mulkalla	20
3	Rapalle	35
4	Vempalle	15
5	Gudipet	22
	TOTAL	120

Selection of the Respondents:

A total of 10% of farmers were selected from each of the three farm size groups in each selected village. In total, there were 120 farmers selected, comprising 51 small farmers, 32 medium farmers, and 17 large farmers, respectively.

Sl.NO	Farmer Category	Land Holding (in Hectare)
1	Marginal	Less than 1
2	Small	1-2
3	Semi-Medium	2-4
4	Medium farmers	4-10
5	Medium farmers	More than 10

Selection of the Markets and its Functionaries The list of market functionaries was derived from the chosen market. Random selection will be used to determine 10% of the total market functionaries. The marketing of agricultural commodities involves various market functionaries/marketing agencies, including:

1. Producers
2. Merchant Middlemen
3. Agent Middlemen

Functionaries	No. of Functionaries
Producer - consumer	2
Producer-wholesaler-retailer-consumer	4

Analytical Tools**Garrett's Ranking Techniques:**

This technique is employed to assess the challenges encountered by the respondents in the sample, as well as their preferences among the provided factors. In this approach, respondents are requested to assign ranks to the given factors. These assigned ranks are then converted into score values using the following formula:

$$\text{Percent position} = 100 * (R_{ij} - 0.5) / N_j$$

Results and Discussion**Table -1 : Constraints faced by farmers in marketing of Groundnut**

Sl. No.	Constraint particulars	Mean score	Rank
1.	Price fluctuation	78.26	I
2.	Absence of grading and processing	41.86	VIII
3.	Inadequate storage facility	63.17	II
4.	Inadequate market and finance	52.20	IV
5.	Indebtedness to trader	44.00	VI
6.	Lack of transport facility	43.53	VII
7.	Lack of market information	46.73	V
8.	Absence of regulated market	22.8	IX
9.	Higher commission charges	60.04	III

An effort has been made to identify the primary challenges faced by coffee growers in the marketing of coffee in Wayanad district, as presented in the table. The data reveals that price fluctuation is the foremost constraint faced by coffee growers, followed by absence of grading and processing (Rank II), inadequate storage facility (Rank III), inadequate market and finance (Rank IV), indebtedness to traders (Rank V), lack of transport facility (Rank VI), lack of market information (Rank VII), absence of regulated market (Rank VIII), and higher commission charges (Rank IX). It is evident from the table that high price fluctuations are the major problem faced by coffee growers, followed by low prices during coffee harvesting season. The price of coffee in the market is greatly influenced by demand and supply conditions. During market glut, coffee prices plummet rapidly, resulting in losses for coffee growers. Additionally, inadequate storage facilities hinder long-term storage of coffee, forcing growers to sell at lower prices in the market. Another significant constraint faced by coffee growers is the high cost of marketing their produce. This may be due to the lack of affordable and efficient transport facilities in the area, which raises overall

marketing costs and results in physical losses during the transportation of the produce from the farm to the wholesale market.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the marketing of groundnut in Mancherial district and emphasizes the need for policy interventions to enhance the efficiency of the marketing system, improve farmers' income, and promote sustainable agriculture. The findings and recommendations of this study underscore the importance of a multi-stakeholder approach involving farmers, government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and other private actors to develop a more efficient and transparent groundnut marketing system. Further research and analysis are necessary to explore the feasibility and potential impact of these recommendations, particularly in light of changing market dynamics and consumer preferences. This study contributes to the existing literature on agricultural marketing and can serve as a valuable resource for scholars, policymakers, and practitioners working in this field. The study delves into the details of groundnut marketing in Mancherial district, specifically analyzing prices, different marketing

channels, costs and contributions of various intermediaries, and estimating the producer's share in the consumer's rupee.

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